

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

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Currently, there are many methods for learning a foreign language in schools. Each of the methods has certain features, some are more popular and in demand, others are less. This article will discuss the basic techniques for learning English by students. In the modern world, English is very popular, moreover, this language is the language of international communication, it is known all over the world. Today, there are a huge number of methods for teaching English. In addition, new ones are regularly developed, so now every teacher can choose the most suitable method of work for himself. The main task pursued by the classical methodology is the formation of the grammatical base of the language being studied. It is worth noting that many schools prefer it. The simplified scheme is as follows - the study of grammar, the basic rules, which are subsequently applied in specific examples and reinforced with the help of exercises. Following the principles of the linguo-socio-cultural method, we can safely say that a foreign language is a kind of mirror in which the way of life, traditions and customs, culture and history of the language are reflected. However, in recent years, in the top of the most popular methods of teaching foreign languages is the communicative method, which occupies the first line in the ratings and calculations of extras. At the moment, the communicative approach is the most relevant method, focused on what fundamentalists are not at all interested in - the practice of communication and the development of language skills. This approach is widespread in Europe and the United States, and now it is the mainstay of the English language curriculum in many schools. The program, built on a communicative approach, does not imply particularly complex or specific vocabulary, complex theorizing about grammar, and boring, time-consuming exercises. Classes are based on imitation of real situations, live, open communication, built on the need to achieve success in communication with another person - as it happens naturally in a child in early childhood. The communicative methodology builds on four of the basic communication skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening comprehension. At the very first level, the greatest attention is paid to understanding and speaking. Translation, as you may have noticed, is not affected at all in this technique, all manuals are originally in English. The fact that the practice of

communication occupies a special place in the communicative methodology is indicated by the name itself. The communicative technique is aimed at developing the skills and abilities of speaking in a foreign language. It should also be noted that the application of the methodology directly affects the structure of the lesson. Very often in the classroom it is necessary to use game situations, conduct group work, develop tasks for finding errors, for the ability to compare and compare. As a rule, such activities make not only memory work actively, Learning is an active interaction between the teacher and students, and it cannot be one-sided. It depends on the teacher how successful the learning process will be. It is obvious that each teacher is guided in accordance with his personal experience in the choice of methods and methods of work. But, based on the results of the experimental work carried out, it can be argued that the use of a variety of techniques within the framework of communicative, inductive, deductive methods gives a positive result and, undoubtedly, contributes to an increase in the effectiveness of teaching grammar. English teaching is an exciting task, as we are multi-lingual and have a diverse socio-economic background. Learners nowadays want more, they are not just contented with one lesson that is repeated over time, they want something new, something that no one has ever talked about, something that they can research about. Using TBL as an approach would encourage the students to do their own research, which is what's expected of them, because for them smart is the new cool. On the other hand, in PPP students are expected to put what they have learned into practice that would lead them into mastering what they have learned for it to slowly become part of their lives. One of the teacher's fear in educating her students is that her students would eventually forget what they have learned, that's why in PPP the teacher encourages her students to produce on their part. The TTT or the Test Teach Test approach, this approach encourages the teacher to give an assessment before teaching and then provide another assessment at the end of the lesson. Since the students nowadays loves challenges, teachers might as well use this approach, just make sure that the content is equal with the assessment that you would provide. These approaches may or may not help the teacher in educating her students, though considered as best approaches, in the end everything would always, always depend on the ability of a teacher. "If you're not having fun, then you're probably doing it wrong." if you don't have the heart to teach then this approaches mean nothing to you. To be a teacher is a difficult job but once you'd get used to it you would know how amazing it is to see your students learn as you teach. Still, general thinking identifies the English language as a mark of being literate. So teachers of this century put together all the

methods to find the best one for our country. Although too much use of visual aids and gamification of education are still not widespread in our country.

References

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